

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PARASITIC PLANTS IN THE BULGARIAN FLORA

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Abstract

The aim of the present study is to provide an inventory and characterization of the parasitic flora on the territory of Bulgaria. The study includes preparation of a list of parasitic plant species in Bulgaria, their classification, biological, phytogeographic characteristics and nature protection status. As a result of the study, 89 parasitic species were found (2.1% of the Bulgarian flora), belonging to 18 genera and 6 families of 1 class Magnoliopsida. Of the families, the richest in species is the Scrophulariaceae family (42 species), and of the genera - the genus *Orobanch* (24 species). Herbaceous species (annual and perennial and their intermediate forms) predominate among biological types (94.4%), and the participation of shrubs is only 5.6%. Most of the established species (66.3%) are distributed in less than half of the floristic regions on the territory of the country, 16.9% of them occur limitedly in 1 or 2 regions. Seven of the studied species have nature protection status. The vertical distribution of species is as follows: in the range 0-500 m a.s.l. 65.2% of species occur; in the range 500-1000 m a.s.l. - 77.5%; 1001-1500 m a.s.l.-66.3%; 1501-2000 m a.s.l.-37.1%; 2001-2500 m.a.s.l.-16.9%; above 2500 m.a.s.l.- 10.1%. Among the parasitic species, the floristic elements of the European type prevail, followed by the Eurasian and Mediterranean types. Regarding their classification, hemiparasites, generalists and root parasites predominate on the territory of the country.

Keywords: hemiparasites, holoparasites, hosts, generalist, specialist, biological type

Introduction

Parasitic plants have repeatedly been documented to play the role of keystone species in the ecosystems [1]. Parasitism has major impacts on host growth, allometry and reproduction, which lead to changes in competitive balances between host and nonhost species and therefore affect community structure, vegetation zonation and population dynamics [2]. According to [3] plant hemiparasites can alter competitive relationships in the host community and change both species and functional diversity, as well as functional trait composition. Parasitic plants are less affected by resource constraints than other plants and most exhibit broad host tolerances, occupy large distributional ranges, and produce high numbers of propagules [4].

The studies concerning the parasitic plants in Bulgaria are mainly limited to the bio-ecological features, distribution and impact of specific taxa such as representatives of genus *Orobanch* [5], *Phelipanche* (= p. *Orobanch*) [6], *Cuscuta* [7,8].

The aim of the present study is to provide an inventory and characterization of the parasitic flora on the territory of Bulgaria.

Materials and methods

The study includes preparation of a list of parasitic plant species in Bulgaria, their classification, biological, phytogeographic characteristics and nature protection status. The classification of parasite species is based on their photosynthetic ability (holoparasites or

hemiparasites), specialization (specialists or generalists), location on the host (stem or root). The taxonomic nomenclature and biological types mainly follow [9], and if necessary, references were made for the synonymy of the species in "The Plant List. A working list of all plant species" (<http://www.theplantlist.org/>) and Euro+Med PlantBase (<http://www.emplantbase.org>). To determine the flora elements and the distribution by floristic regions and the vertical distribution of the species, the "Synopsis of the higher flora in Bulgaria" [10] was used. The territory of Bulgaria is divided into 29 floristic regions and sub-regions. The present study provides information in what proportion of the total number of regions a given parasite species occurs as follows: limited (in 1 to 3 regions) in less than 1/3, between 1/3 and 1/2, between 1/2 and 2/3, in more than 2/3 or in all floristic regions and sub-regions. The conservation status of the species is according to the Red Data Book of the Republic of Bulgaria. Vol. 1. Plants [11] and Biological Diversity Act [12]. Species host data are from [3], [5], [9], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17].

Results

As a result of the study, 89 parasitic species were found, belonging to 18 genera and 6 families of 1 class Magnoliopsida (Table 1). Of the families, the richest in species is the Scrophulariaceae family (42 species), and of the genera - the genus *Orobanch* (24 species), *Pedicularis* (11), *Cuscuta* (10), *Euphrasia* (9), *Rhynanthus* (7), *Thesium* (7) and *Melampyrum* (6).

Table 1.

List of parasitic species from the Bulgarian flora

Species	Floristic regions	Floristic* element	Altitude range (m a.s.l.)	Photosynthetic ability	Range of hosts	Location on host
fam. <i>Cuscutaceae</i>						
<i>Cuscuta approximata</i> Bab.	>1/3,<1/2	Med-NAm	200-1500	holoparasite	generalist	stem
<i>C. campestris</i> Yunker	all regions	Adv (NAm)	0-1800	holoparasite	generalist	stem
<i>C. cesatiana</i> Bertol.	limited	Kos	0-300	holoparasite	generalist	stem
<i>C. epilinum</i> Weihe	limited	Eur-As	0-800	holoparasite	specialist	stem
<i>C. epithimum</i> (L.) L.	>2/3	Eur	0-1800	holoparasite	generalist	stem
<i>C. europaea</i> L.	all regions	subBoreal	0-2600	holoparasite	generalist	stem
<i>C. lupuliformis</i> Krockner	limited	Eur-As	0-300	holoparasite	generalist	stem
<i>C. monogyna</i> Vahl.	>2/3	Eur-As	0-1500	holoparasite	generalist	stem
<i>C. planiflora</i> Ten.	<1/3	Med	200-1500	holoparasite	generalist	stem
<i>C. trifolii</i> Bab.	limited	subMed	0	holoparasite	generalist	stem
fam. <i>Loranthaceae</i>						
<i>Arceuthobium oxycedri</i> (D.C.) M. Bieb.	>1/3,<1/2	Eur-As	0-800	hemiparasite	specialist	stem
<i>Loranthus europaeus</i> Jacq.	>1/2,<2/3	Pont-Med	0-1500	hemiparasite	specialist	stem
<i>Viscum album</i> L.	all regions	Eur-As	500-1300	hemiparasite	generalist	stem
<i>V. laxum</i> Boiss. & Reut.	<1/3	Eur-As	1000-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	stem
fam. <i>Orobanchaceae</i>						
<i>Orobanche aegyptiaca</i> Pers.	limited	Med-CAs	0-1000	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. alba</i> Stephan ex Willd.	>2/3	Eur-Med	0-2000	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. alsatica</i> Kirschl	<1/3	subMed-CAs	0-100	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. amethystea</i> Thuill.	>1/3,<1/2	Med-OT	0-2000	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. arenaria</i> Borkh.	<1/3	Eur-Med	0-850	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. caryophyllaceae</i> Sm.	>1/3,<1/2	Eur	0-1100	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. crenata</i> Forskai	<1/3	Med	0-1800	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. cumana</i> Wallr.	<1/3	Med-Sib	0-600	holoparasite	specialist	root
<i>O. elatior</i> Sutton	<1/3	Eur-CAs	0-1800	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. esulae</i> Pančić	<1/3	Bal	0-700	holoparasite	specialist	root
<i>O. gracilis</i> Sm.	>1/2,<2/3	Eur-Med	0-2500	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. loricata</i> Reichenb.	<1/3	subMed	0-1100	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. lutea</i> Baumg.	>1/3,<1/2	Eur-As	0-1000	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. minor</i> Sm.	>1/3,<1/2	Med	0-2000	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. mutelii</i> F. W. Schultz	>1/3,<1/2	Med-OT	0-1000	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. nana</i> (Reuter) Noë ex G. Beck	<1/3	Eur-Med	0-1100	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. oxyloba</i> (Reuter) G. Beck	>1/3,<1/2	Med-CAs	0-1200	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. pancicii</i> Beck	<1/3	Bal	0-1400	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. pubescens</i> d'Urv.	>1/3,<1/2	Med	0-750	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. purpurea</i> Jacq.	>2/3	Eur	0-1300	holoparasite	specialist	root

<i>O. ramosa</i> L.	>2/3	Eur-Med	0-1400	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. reticulata</i> Wallr.	>1/2,<2/3	Eur	0-1700	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. serbica</i> Beck & Petrovic	limited	Bal	600-1000	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. teucrii</i> Holandre	<1/3	subMed	250-1100	holoparasite	generalist	root
fam. <i>Raflesiaceae</i>						
<i>Cytinus clusii</i> (Nyman) Gand.	limited	Med	0-300	holoparasite	specialist	root
fam. <i>Santalaceae</i>						
<i>Osyris alba</i> L.	<1/3	Med	0-1000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Thesium alpinum</i> L.	>1/3,<1/2	Eur-Med	1500-2500	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>T. arvense</i> Horvatovszky	all regions	Med-CAs	0-1100	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>T. bavarum</i> Schrank	all regions	subMed	500-2500	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>T. divaricatum</i> Jan ex Mert. & Koch	all regions	Eur-Med	0-1600	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>T. dollineri</i> Murb.	>1/2,<2/3	Pont	0-1000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>T. linophyllon</i> L.	<1/3	subMed	800-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>T. simplex</i> Velen.	<1/3	Bal-Dac	0-1200	hemiparasite	generalist	root
fam. <i>Scrophulariaceae</i>						
<i>Bartsia alpina</i> L.	limited	Boreal	2100-2600	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Euphrasia drosocalyx</i> (<i>E. minima</i> x <i>E. rostkoviana</i>)	limited	Alp-Carp-Bal	2000-2900	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>E. hirtella</i> Jordan ex Reuter	>1/3,<1/2	Eur-As	800-2500	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>E. liburnica</i> Wettst.	>1/3,<1/2	Carp-Bal	500-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>E. minima</i> Jacq ex DC	>1/3,<1/2	Alp-Carp-Bal	2000-2900	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>E. pectinata</i> Ten.	>1/2,<2/3	subMed	400-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>E. picta</i> Wimm	>2/3	subMed	500-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>E. rostkoviana</i> Hayne	all regions	Eur-As	200-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>E. salisburgensis</i> Funck	>1/3,<1/2	subMed	1000-2500	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>E. stricta</i> D.Wolff ex J.F.Lehm.	all regions	Eur	700-2100	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Lathraea rhodopaea</i> Dingler	<1/3	Bal	200-1650	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>L. squamaria</i> L.	all regions	Eur-As	0-2000	holoparasite	generalist	root
<i>M. bihariense</i> Kern.	<1/3	Eur	0-1000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>M. cristatum</i> L.	all regions	Eur-Sib	0-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>M. pratense</i> L.	all regions	Eur-Sib	0-1600	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>M. scardicum</i> Wettst.	>2/3	Bal	600-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>M. sylvaticum</i> L.	all regions	Eur	600-2200	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Melampyrum arvense</i> L.	all regions	Eur-Med	0-1000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Odontites glutinosa</i> (Bieb.) Bentham	>1/3,<1/2	Pont-Med	200-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>O. verna</i> (Bellardi) Dumortier	limited	Eur-As	0-1600	hemiparasite	generalist	root

<i>O. lutea</i> (L.) Clairv.	all regions	Eur	300-1800	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Parentucellia latifolia</i> (L.) Caruel	all regions	Med	0-1000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Pedicularis comosa</i> L.	<1/3	Eur-Med	0-1300	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. grisebachii</i> Wettst.	<1/3	Bal	100-1500	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. hoermanniana</i> K.Malý	<1/3	Bal-Ap	1300-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. leucodon</i> Griseb.	>1/3,<1/2	Bal	0-1000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. moesiaca</i> Stadlm.	<1/3	Bal	200-1200	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. occulta</i> Janka	limited	Bal	1000-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. oederi</i> Vahl.	limited	Arct-Alp	2000-2900	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. orthantha</i> Griseb.	<1/3	Bal	1400-2500	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. palustris</i> L.	limited	Eur-As	500-1000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. petiolaris</i> Ten.	<1/3	Ap-Bal	1000-2500	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>P. verticillata</i> L.	<1/3	Boreal	1000-2900	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Rhinanthus alpinus</i> Baumg.	>1/3,<1/2	Alp-Carp-Bal	2000-2900	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Rh. angustifolius</i> C. C. Gmel.	>1/2,<2/3	Eur	800-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Rh. gracilis</i> Schur	limited	Eur	1500	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Rh. javorkae</i> Soó	limited	Bul	2000-2900	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Rh. minor</i> L.	<1/3	Eur-Sib	0-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Rh. rumelicus</i> Velen.	all regions	Eur-Med	0-1200	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Rh. Wagneri</i> Degen	>1/2,<2/3	subMed	1000-2900	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Rhynchocorys elephas</i> (L.) Griseb.	<1/3	subMed	1000-2000	hemiparasite	generalist	root
<i>Tozzia carpatica</i> Waloszcz.	<1/3	Alp-Med	1000-2900	hemiparasite	generalist	root

*Abbreviations and full names of the floristic elements are presented in Table 2

Herbaceous species (annual and perennial and their intermediate forms) predominate among biological types (94.4%), and the participation of shrubs is only

5.6%. Among the parasitic species in the country, there are no representatives of semi-shrubs and trees (Figure 1.)

Figure 1. Distribution of species by biological types

Most of the established species (66.3%) are distributed in less than half of the floristic regions on the territory of the country, 16.9% of them occur limitedly in 1 or 2 regions, and among them there are also cosmopolitan species such as *Cuscuta cesatiana*, as well as

endemic species such as *Rhinanthus javorkae* and *Pedicularis occulta*, and also with nature protection status (Fig. 2). The majority of species (18,0%) found in all floristic regions are of the European type.

Figure 2. Horizontal distribution of parasitic species in the floristic regions on the territory of the country (by proportion of the total number of floristic regions a given parasite species occurs)

Seven of the studied species have nature protection status. The Bulgarian Red Book includes 5 species in the following categories: **Critically Endangered** (*Cytinus clusii* and *Pedicularis palustris*), **Endangered** (*Rhinanthus javorkae*, *Pedicularis oederi*), **Vulnerable** (*Tozzia carpatica*). Three of the listed species (*C. clusii*, *P. palustris*, *T. carpatica*) are included in Biological Diversity Act, together with *Rhynchospora elephas* and *Lathraea rhodopaea*.

The vertical distribution of species is as follows: in the range 0-500 m a.s.l. 65.2% of species occur; in

the range 500-1000 m a.s.l. - 77.5%; 1001-1500 m a.s.l.-66.3%; 1501-2000 m a.s.l.-37.1%; 2001-2500 m.a.s.l.-16.9%; above 2500 m.a.s.l- 10.1%.

Among the parasitic species, the floristic elements of the European type prevail, followed by the Eurasian and Mediterranean types, which is largely equivalent to the phytogeographic distribution of the species of the flora of Bulgaria. A high presence of Balkan endemics has been registered (Table 2).

Table 2.

Distribution of floristic elements			
Floristic elements	Abbreviation	Number	%
1. EUROPEAN TYPE		22	24,7%
1.1. European typical	Eur	11	12,4%
1.2. European-Mediterranean	Eur-Med	10	11,2%
2. EURASIAN TYPE		15	16,9%
2.1. European-Asian	Eur-As	12	13,5%
2.2. European-Siberian	Eur-Sib	3	3,4%
3. SUBMEDITERRANEAN TYPE		11	12,4%
3.1. Sub-Mediterranean typical	SubMed	10	11,2%
3.2. Sub-Mediterranean-Asiatic	SubMed-CAs	1	1,1%
4. MEDITERRANEAN TYPE		14	15,7%
4.1. Mediterranean typical	Med	7	7,9%
4.2. Mediterranean-Siberian	Med-Sib	1	1,1%
4.3. Mediterranean-Central Asian	Med-CAs	3	3,4%
4.4. Mediterranean-Oriental Turanian	Med-OT	2	2,2%
4.5. Apennine-North American	Med-Nam	1	1,1%
5. PONTIC TYPE		3	3,4%
5.1. Pontic typical	Pont	1	1,1%
5.5. Pontic-Mediterranean	Pont-Med	2	2,2%
6. BOREAL TYPE		3	3,4%
6.1. Boreal	Boreal	2	2,2%
6.2. Subboreal	SubBoreal	1	1,1%
7. ALPINE TYPE		5	5,6%
7.1. Alpine-Carpathian-Balkan	Alp-Carp-Bal	3	3,4%

7.2. Alpine-Mediterranean	Alp-Med	1	1,1%
7.3. Arctoalpine	Arct-Alp	1	1,1%
8. BALKAN SUBENDEMIC TYPE		4	4,5%
8.3. Balkan-Dacian	Bal-Dac	1	1,1%
8.4. Apenninian-Balkan	Ap-Bal	2	2,2%
8.5. Carpatho-Balkan	Carp-Bal	1	1,1%
9. ENDEMIC TYPE		11	12,4%
9.1. Balkan	Bal	10	11,2%
9.2. Bulgarian	Bul	1	1,1%
10. COSMOPOLITAN TYPE	Kos	1	1,1%
11. ADVENTIVE TYPE	Adv	1	1,1%
TOTAL		89	100,0%

The ratio (in %) of the number of holoparasitic to hemiparasitic species of the flora of Bulgaria is 41.6:58.4. The majority of holoparasites are representatives of the genus *Orobanch* (64.9%) and the genus *Cuscuta* (27.1%). Genera *Pedicularis* (21.1%), *Euphrasia* (17.3%), *Rhynanthus* (13.5%) and *Thesium* (13.5%) have the greatest diversity of hemiparasites. Regarding the range of hosts, generalists (92.1%) prevail over specialists (7.9%). Within the framework of the generalists, different groups of more narrowly specialized holoparasites and hemiparasites can be distinguished - distributed in certain biological types such as herbaceous plants (*Cuscuta europaea*, *C. campestris* и др.), trees (*Cuscuta lupuliformis*, *Lathrea* sp., deciduous- *Viscum album*, conifers- *V. laxum*) or only by representatives of certain genera (*Orobancha panicii* on species of the genera *Ligustrum*, *Scabiosa*, *Euonymus*, *O. teucrii*- on *Teucrium* sp., *Thymus* sp. and *Satureia* sp.) and families (*Cuscuta trifoli*- on *Fabaceae*, *Orobancha arenaria*- on *Fabaceae*, *Asteraceae*, *Tozzia carpatica*- on *Asteraceae* u др.). Examples for specialists are *Arceuthobium oxycedri*, which occurs only in species of *Juniperus* sp.; *Orobancha purpurea*- on *Achillea* sp., *O. esulae*- on *Euphorbia* sp., *Cytinus clusii* on *Cistus incani*.

According to location on hosts, the majority of species (84.2%) are root parasites and 25.8% are stem parasites. Among the stem parasites, holoparasites dominate (71.4%) over hemiparasites (28.6%), while the opposite is observed in root parasites - predominance of hemiparasites (64.0%) over holoparasites (36.0%).

Discussion

According to [18] approximately 1,2% of all flowering plant species are parasitic. The participation of these species in Bulgarian flora is 2.1%. Parasitic angiosperms are found in 16 families and live in diverse habitats, ranging from tropical forests to arctic islands [19] and representatives of 6 of them or more than 1/3 of the families are found in the flora of Bulgaria). The family *Scrophulariaceae* is the richest family in parasitic species [20], and *Orobanch*, the type genus of the family *Orobanchaceae*, contains almost 200 species of small parasitic herbaceous plants, mostly native to the temperate Northern Hemisphere [21]

The distribution of the biological types in the parasitic plants corresponds to their distribution in the flora of Bulgaria, where herbaceous species (annual and perennial) are about 90%, as well as to the fact that among them the parasites predominate by families composed

mainly of herbaceous species such are Asteraceae, Fabaceae, Apiaceae, Lamiaceae, Solanaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Brassicaceae, Malvaceae, etc.

The higher participation of European and Eurasian floristic elements can be explained by the geographical location of the country. The large number of endemic species is an indicator of active morphogenetic processes in the past and their relationship with similar processes in hosts needs to be further investigated. It could be said that the horizontal distribution of parasitic species is more limited by their ranges, while the vertical distribution is rather determined by the altitudinal range of their hosts.

The predominance of stem-over root-parasites is not unusual based on [22], according to which stem parasites occur in several families, but root parasites are more common and occur in various taxonomic groups. The same is true for the dominant presence of generalists over specialists and hemiparasitic over holoparasitic species. Compared with hemiparasitic plants, holoparasitic plants depend completely on their hosts for survival, with higher host specificity [23]. In this regard, holoparasites are much more sensitive to changes in environmental factors related to climate, successions (natural and anthropogenic), which determine their distribution and biodiversity.

Conclusions

The study showed that the flora of Bulgaria contains a wide variety of parasitic plants, many of which are endemic. Among them, there are both widespread and in many cases dangerous for wild and cultivated plants species, as well as those with a limited range of populations and the highest category of nature protection status. Regarding their classification, hemiparasites, generalists and root parasites predominate on the territory of the country.

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References:

1. Těšitel, J., Li, A., Knotková, K., McLellan, R., Bandaranayake, P., Watson, D. 2021. The bright side of parasitic plants: what are they good for? Plant

- Physiol, 185(4), 1309-1324. doi: 10.1093/plphys/kiia069. PMID: 33793868; PMCID: PMC8133642.
2. Press, M, Phoenix, G. 2005. Impacts of parasitic plants on natural communities. *The New Phytologist* 166 (3), 737–751. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2005.01358.x>
 3. Chaudron, C., Mazalová, M., Kuras, T., Malenovský, I. Mládek, J. 2021. Introducing ecosystem engineers for grassland biodiversity conservation: A review of the effects of hemiparasitic *Rhinanthus* species on plant and animal communities at multiple trophic levels. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics*, 52, 125633, ISSN 1433-8319, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ppees.2021.125633>.
 4. Watson, D. 2009. Determinants of parasitic plant distribution: The role of host quality. *Botany* 87(1), 16-21.
 5. Stoyanov, K. 2005. Floristic materials and critical notes on the genus *Orobancha* subgen. *Phelipanche* in Bulgaria. *Flora Mediterranea*, 15, 461-476. ISSN 1120-4052.
 6. Hristeva, T, Dekalska, T., Bozhinova, R. 2014. Weeds and Root Parasite Broomrape Nutrient Uptake in Oriental Tobacco Crop. *Plant Science*, 2-3, 67-71.
 7. Zagorchev, L., Albanova, I., Tosheva, A., Li, J., Teofanova, D. 2018. Salinity effect on *Cuscuta campestris* Yunck. parasitism on *Arabidopsis thaliana* L. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*. 132, 408-414. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plaphy.2018.09.037>
 8. Zagorchev, L., Traianova, A., Teofanova, D., Li, J., Kouzmanova, M., Goltsev, V. 2020. Influence of *Cuscuta campestris* Yunck. on the photosynthetic activity of *Ipomoea tricolor* Cav. – in vivo chlorophyll a fluorescence assessment. *Photosynthetica*. 58 (SI): 237-247. DOI: 10.32615/ps.2020.004
 9. Delipavlov, D., Chesmedziev, I., Popova, M., Terzijski, D., Kovachev, I. 2003. Genus *Galanthus*. In: Delipavlov D., editor. *Determinant of Plant in Bulgaria*. Agricultural University; Plovdiv, 452–453. [in Bulgarian]
 10. Asyov, B., Petrova, A., Dimitrov, D. 2012. *Conspectus of the Bulgarian Vascular Flora: Distribution Maps and Floristic Elements*. 4. Sofia, Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation, p. 351.
 11. Peev, D. Petrova, A., Anchev, M., Temnikova, D., Denchev, C., Ganeva, A., Gushev, Ch., Vladimirov, V. (eds). 2015. *Red Data Book of the Republic of Bulgaria*. Vol. 1. Plants and Fungi. BAS & MoEW, Sofia [English ed.: ISBN 978-954-9746-21-1.
 12. *Biological Diversity Act Promulgated*, State Gazette No. 77/9.08.2002, last amended 18.07.2017 (in Bulgarian).
 13. Kojić, M, Maširević, S., Jovanović, D. 2001. Distribution and biodiversity of Broomrape (*Orobancha* l.) worldwide and in Serbia. *Helia*, 24, 35, 73-92.
 14. Qasem, J. 2006. Host range of the parasitic weed *Osyris alba* L. in Jordan. *Weed Biol. Manag.* 6, 74–78.
 15. CABI Digital library. 2024. <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/10.1079/cabicompendium.37745>
 16. Brown, M., Moore, P., Twyford, A. 2021. Performance of generalist hemiparasitic *Euphrasia* across a phylogenetically diverse host spectrum. *New Phytol.* 232, 2165–2174.
 17. Walker, K. 2015. *Bartsia alpina* L. Alpine Bartsia. *Species Account*. Botanical Society of Britain and Ireland.
 18. Twyford, A. 2018. Parasitic plants, *Current Biology*, 28, 16, 857-859, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2018.06.030>
 19. Young, N., Steiner, K., DePamphilis, C. 1999. The evolution of parasitism in scrophulariaceae/orobanchaceae: Plastid gene sequences refute an evolutionary transition series. *Annals of the Missouri Botanical Garden*, 86(4), 876-893. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2666173>
 20. Nickrent, D. 2002. Plantas parásitas en el mundo. Capítulo 2, pp. 7-27 In J. A. LópezSáez, P. Catalán and L. Sáez [eds.], *Plantas Parásitas de la Península Ibérica e Islas Baleares*. Mundi-Prensa Libros, S. A., Madrid.
 21. Beck-Mannagetta, G. 1930. *Orobanchaceae*. In Engler, A. (ed.) *Das Pflanzenreich* 4: 1-348.
 22. Nickrent, D., Musselman, L. 2004. *Introduction to Parasitic Flowering Plants*. The Plant Health Instructor. <http://www.ap-snet.org/edcenter/intropp/PathogenGroups/Pages/ParasiticPlants.aspx> <http://dx.doi.org/10.1094/PHI-I-2004-0330-01>
 23. Andrea, C., Sergi, M.-B. 2021. Holoparasitic plant-host interactions and their impact on Mediterranean ecosystems. *Plant Physiol.* 185, 1325–1338. doi: 10.1093/plphys/kiab030